

**BM5102 | ORGANIZATIONAL BEHAVIOUR
SEMESTER 1 2020/2021
REFLECTIVE REPORT**

Name	: Dk. Nurul Hakimah @ Dk. Khadizah bte Pg. Metussin
Student ID	: 20M1260
Email	: 20M1260@ubd.edu.bn
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1. What were the project goals and how did you attempt to achieve them? Describe your project plan and how it addressed the requirements of the assignment and your broader area of practice.

- **Project Goals:** My main goal is to obtain the specific information within the scheduled time and ensure the quality of the paper to be readable as well as informative. The long-term goal of the research is to develop awareness in order to stimulate widen interest in and understanding the context. According to Power JL (2011), Cultural diversity can be defined as “*sharing motives, beliefs, values, interpretations and identities as well as common experiences on the meanings of significant events*”. The objective of this study is to come up with the employee’s opinion, their decision-making process with in a scope of literature review and the relation practices by the company with regards of discrimination in the workplace and outline the study of employees’ adaptation on incompatible working styles. Specifically, the study has the sub-objectives; to develop cross-cultural employees’ practices and researches with regards to their acceptance of tolerant with the discrimination and challenges, to review current company research and practices regarding cultural diversity in the workplace, to obtain a particular working style and characteristics of cultural diversity that is found on Pezzo and Sugarbun. The data collected from this study will be useful to other companies as well as related employees in developing better action taken into account and neutralization for diversification of culture in the workplace.
- **The How:** I’ve been working under Satami Group at Pezzo before as a Management Trainee for 11 months. At first, I asked the head of Branch if it is possible if I want to conduct research on both Sugarbun and Pezzo. When she said yes, “*sure can, just prepare a permission letter.*” Moreover, I also asked the management team if they’re okay with interviews. They give positive feedback and even ask me for my free time so they could arrange the interview time with me. Aside from that, I’m a bit hesitant to carry on with the research as it might involve sensitivity however with the support and positivity circle let me continue to conduct the research. I also ran a pilot test on the two employees of Satami Food andCatering services who’s incharge of Pezzo and Sugarbun before proceeding to online questionnaires and interviews.
- **Project Plan:** Firstly a topic, I need a topic or specific subject so I can focus on or else I'll be in confusion and not well organized. I’ve come up with numerous topics that I could relate on with cultural diversity in the workplace that includes the discrimination and working style, bullying. Once I decided on the topic and a research question, I've moved to the proposal plan on what measures I should take next. That includes my main objective, why this topic interests me as suggested by my lecturer and make sure the topic makes us overwhelmed. I tried to search for information if there were any relevant documents, journal articles with regards to this type of subject. Thankfully, I am able to obtain numerous articles that can be related. I also asked my previous head of branch and co-workers if they’re okay if I want to conduct an interview and online survey. At first, I only planned to carry out an online questionnaire due to their busy schedule, however in the end I added additional information and conducted an interview only with the head managers instead of the service crew. For the secondary data, data is gathered

through reading resources which for instance journal articles in order to gain more information for the types and challenges of working in different types of working styles as well as discrimination in the workplace. The design of the study was designed using a descriptive quantitative analysis system where data collection and analysis were conducted to meet the objectives of the study. The scope of research took about a month due to time constraint in the case of Pezzo and Sugarbun in Brunei: A study of employees' adaptation on incompatible working styles aren't frequently published.

- **Area of practice:** Mainly focusing on the employees of Pezzo and Sugarbun under Satami Food and Catering services in Brunei due to Pandemic COVID-19, there are limitations on doing primary data.
2. What did you learn? Connect theoretical knowledge from your course to the practical work you undertook. Discuss how particular actions reflect major theories in your field.
- **Mode of learning:** I've learned how to write a proper research paper with a proper guideline from the lecturer. This could enhance my capability, motivation and decision making process. I also learned the personality of people, how they handle their stress, and what their solutions are when they face issues. Moreover, how to search for journal articles and the method was shared quite beneficial especially for students who have never done research before.
 - **Theoretical knowledge:** By working in a productive environment at Pezzo last time, respectful, feeling of inclusiveness and friendly setting. This slowly made me gain interest in management to learn more theoretically as I practically experienced it. Incentives were given if we reach the target, this made me always want to do a good job to reach their expectations. The mixture of Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivations had driven me to finish up the research project I've been working on.
3. What did you do and feel? Describe your own opinions about the project, including choices that were made and actions that were taken. What were your own contributions and why did you perform in the way that you did?
- At first, I feel unsure whether it's on the right track of the research paper. Starting to lose confidence and emotionally unstable, however I refer back to guidelines just in case I've missed certain points that are required on the research paper. Probably, due to my experience as a worker there had driven me to conduct this research as the case had interested me to the extent out of curiosity if there is an issue of this topic in the company.
 - **Opinions:** Since the COVID-19 crisis, there are various issues that arose for instance employees' salary cut off, dissatisfaction of employees. I think by doing research on the incompatible working styles despite the cultural differences is somehow unique and rarely been focused on especially in

Brunei food and beverages company case, most people usually focus on the challenges they faced during this crisis, might as well the behaviour of the employees working in the company.

- **Contributions:** Comparing secondary data mainly from journal articles done by several researchers that have done similar research studies, such as those in the information and management journals. The paper will then discuss the literature and find answers to the research questions, which will help in dissecting and analysing the research topic. Obtain approval to conduct an online questionnaire and interviews at Satami. I also do a pilot test beforehand and get an approval.
 - **Reason:** By gaining the data from questionnaires seems something is missing or off, I decided at the very last minute to support my data by conducting an interview. Luckily, the one I interviewed was willing to give full cooperation and provide the answer that I've been searching on.
4. What did others do and feel? If this is a group project, discuss the opinions that other group members conveyed to you, and the actions they took. Did you disagree about any points, and if so how did you resolve these issues?
- It is such an interesting case since it relates to an individual experiencing adapting with different working styles. This can be incorporated like us working together despite different working styles but manage to settle it down. As long as we're on the right flows the work can be done without problem. I do disagree at some points where they're expecting an extended submission. However, if it's a group project I usually ask each of them what they feel about whether they agree or disagree, is it okay to input this on the data or not and more. We've shared our knowledge, contributing our own ideas and few members quite expert on boosting to point out certain issues. Moreover if there is a disagreement, rather go for majority choice what is good to us is also good for our team projects.
5. What was the outcome? Critically assess the success or failure of your practical work. Point out the ways that it benefited users, and/or met the project objectives.
- **Outcome:** The outcome of my research studied up to my satisfaction, however I am unsure whether it can reach those standards to be called a research paper. The data I obtained quite informative especially from the interviews itself and extra information was given by the interviewees. Moreover, the employees had voiced out their opinion on the questionnaires which I feel somehow the company should've taken measures and solutions for the issues. Some of the findings contain sensitivity where I have to be careful on writing up the information.
 - **Success of failures:** I believe my practical work is successful as I managed to interview three of the head management outlets and office of Satami employees. The information they gave me are very informative and detailed although they did refuse to touch on the sensitive issues but the manage to

give information that is valuable and relatable. With regards to Questionnaires, it was also a success, as the employees share their own experience and opinion despite working in culturally diverse and incompatible working styles.

- **Benefit:** With this practical work, it has boosted up my confidence to approach people, more interactively and open. It also improves my communication skills and gains more knowledge as well as new ideas keep coming. It has sharpened my ability interviewing people and writing skills.

6. What were your personal strengths and weaknesses that were revealed? What have you learned about your own professional development from this project? What skill areas do you still need to develop?

- **Strengths:** Ability to work under pressure and submit right on time. I am also good at organizing stuff, a team player and can do multitasking as well as quite attentive to details. Moreover, the ability to summarise and be good at paraphrasing and pushing myself to do the task given with my own motivations. I also like to ask others if I have any enquiries if I shorten ideas, sharing knowledge.
- **Weaknesses:** Lack of confidence, in the past I have sometimes struggled with confidence and voicing out my opinion. Intimidated with other colleagues as they seem to have more better ideas and plans as well as better English.
- **Professional development:** The ability to voice out my own opinion, approaching people (the company employee), Organized daily routines.
- **Skills to develop:** Polishing my writing skills as well, attentive to every details data that've been obtained

7. What would you do differently next time?

I think only a few changes should've been improved by reading more articles and finding an area of interest to find another interesting topic that could've been done that is relatable with management. Interviewing more people, not just the upper management as well the employees under them so I am able to do comparisons between both sides. Ask myself to regain focus and use my time well, as sometimes I've been busy with family events and business online. Time management is quite important if I've missed a single time it would turn my day upside down and gain no information as well as unable to finish my job on time.

A reflective report is quite essential as it gives the students to reflect on what they've done missing a point or even room for improvement. This could enhance their skills in the future research project or other tasks. The students could refer back on what their main objective is and dig more on the objective they focus on. Moreover, it also can polishing their writing skills, grammar and more data that can be obtained. With this reflective report, this could also let the students be able to see their weaknesses and strengthen their weaknesses and be aware of what is missing as well as the needs to improve.

References:

Power, J. L., et. al. (2011). Acceptability of workplace bullying: A comparative study on six continents, *Journal of Business Research*.